

ADVERTISING TEXTS AND ITS TRANSLATION

Isakova Nargizakhon Valijon qizi

2nd year student of

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

***ANNOTATION.** This article provides information on the study of advertising texts in linguistics, linguistic analysis of their features, why advertising texts are actually needed, the characteristics of advertising texts and their translations. An interesting aspect of the advertising text is that it serves not only to stimulate the consumption of the population, but also to convey certain social, educational or cultural values through it.*

***Keywords:** advertising texts, television, media, internet, translation.*

An advertisement text is a form of written or typewritten advertisement that intends to share a narrative about a product. This comes into the form of an ad copy. Texts may appear through captions of social media posts, billboards, posters, or fliers that market the brand.

We all know that a picture is worth a thousand words, but what happens when the picture is out of position or out of context, or if it doesn't convey any meaning at all? We do indeed waste our time and effort. Our work must contain a decent advertising language that satisfies all of its requirements in addition to an image.

In the modern linguistic literature, you can find a number of definitions of the word "advertising". V.V. Uchenova writes that the loud screams of city reporters about the most important current events are the source of the Latin verb *resamare*, meaning to shout; and the name of the advertising event became a derivative of this verb. "Advertising is a network of mass communication, according to which informational-figurative, expressive-offer works are created and distributed, which are directed to

groups of people in order to select and motivate the advertiser" ["Sotsialnaya reklama. Uchebnoe posobie "Uchenova V. V., Staryx N. V. : Moscow ,. 78-s].

The amount and volume of information conveyed has a profound effect on the way information is received and processed. Excessive information in advertising, on the contrary, their inadequacy has a significant impact on the purchase of the product. It follows that the activation of cognitive need remains a strong psychological factor in advertising [2, 48].

It is content that aims to catch consumers' attention, compel them to do an action that fits with the goals of our advertising campaign, and encourages them to purchase our good or service. They are texts with a strong capacity for persuasion and for commercial reasons, therefore every marketing strategy must take them into account. Every ad or advertisement needs to include marketing copy that reaches the target market and opens doors to sales.

Remember that advertising text should be clear, simple, concise, original, coherent, new ideas, and, above all, generate a significant impact on the public. In copywriting, there are two main groups of advertising text: argumentative copy and narrative copy. Argumentative-descriptive. These works are built on arguments to persuade the intended audience, as the name implies. Additionally, the message is descriptive and explains the features of the good or service as a component of the justification. The cell phone and technology device industries regularly use this style of combative advertising copy. These are the brands that make an effort to persuade customers by outlining features, distinctions, and other details.

Narratives. Brands that appeal to emotionality and feelings use narrative advertising copy for their campaigns. This is due to the use of narrative and stories as an element to connect with the receiver. One brand that uses this type of advertising copy is Coca-Cola.

The act of transforming an advertisement created for a particular audience into a format that appeals to a group of people who speak a different language is known as advertising translation. Ad material must be contextualized and culturally adjusted

when being translated in order to effectively engage target audience. Advertising text is the informational message intended to pique the target audience's interest in a good or service. The translation of advertisements must be proficient from the perspectives of both linguistic standards and marketing strategies. The requirement for their modification to cultural traits, mentalities, and pertinent trends for the foreign target audience is the distinguishing aspect of the translation of advertisements. It takes either target language proficiency or creative ability to complete the translation. The content on brochures, booklets, and leaflets, as well as presentations and messages in the media, on websites and bulletin boards, etc., are all examples of campaigns for the promotion of goods.

When a business enters foreign markets for sales as well as for international partners and investors, translation of marketing materials is necessary. Translation will also be essential if the target audience includes immigrants from other countries. Strict control over the translation's semantic component is required. Otherwise, the following errors could occur:

- inappropriate tracing-paper from a foreign language;
- incorrect interpretation of the name of a brand.

The essential requirement of translating commercials is to concentrate on the message rather than the words alone. When it comes to translating advertising, taking a literal approach might be a significant mistake that could lead to a disastrous campaign as well as a weak one.

According to R. Reeves, a specialist in advertising, the consumer remembers only one clear proof or one clear idea from the text of the advertisement [3, 27].

The English language has a large vocabulary, which is well-known. Without a strong vocabulary, advertising is boring. It cannot open up consumer markets for a brand. These words should be associated with the brand that is most likely to draw customers. Advertising language is simply a combination of extra linguistic and linguistic means of expression governed by mass communication laws and general literary rules, as well as a unique language structure that allows the addressee to

understand specific information while taking into account the cultural, sociological, and psycholinguistic features of the language. The primary communicative goal of the advertising text is to persuade the reader to select the promoted goods and services.

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